

1 **Selecting mixtures on the basis of dietary exposure and hazard data:**
2 **application to pesticide exposure in the European population in relation to**
3 **steatosis**

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31
32 **Abstract**

33
34 Populations are exposed to mixtures of pesticides through their diet on a daily basis. The
35 question of which substances should be assessed together remains a major challenge due to the
36 complexity of the mixtures. In addition, the associated risk is difficult to characterise. The
37 EuroMix project (European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures) has developed
38 a strategy for mixture risk assessment. In particular, it has proposed a methodology that
39 combines exposures and hazard information to identify relevant mixtures of chemicals
40 belonging to any cumulative assessment group (CAG) to which the European population is
41 exposed via food. For the purposes of this study, food consumption and pesticide residue data
42 in food and drinking water were obtained from national surveys in nine European countries.
43 Mixtures of pesticides were identified by a sparse non-negative matrix underestimation
44 (SNMU) applied to the specific liver steatosis effect in children from 11 to 15 years of age, and
45 in adults from 18 to 64 years of age in nine European countries. Exposures and mixtures of 144
46 pesticides were evaluated through four different scenarios: (1) chronic exposure with a merged
47 concentration dataset in the adult population, (2) chronic exposure with country-specific
48 concentration datasets in the adult population, (3) acute exposure with a merged concentration
49 dataset in the adult population, and (4) chronic exposure with a merged concentration dataset
50 in the paediatric population. The relative potency factors of each substance were calculated to

51 express their potency relative to flusilazole, which was chosen as the reference compound. The
52 selection of mixtures and the evaluation of exposures for each country were carried out using
53 the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) software.

54 Concerning chronic exposure, one mixture explained the largest proportion of the total variance
55 for each country, while in acute exposure, several mixtures were often involved. The results
56 showed that there were 15 main pesticides in the mixtures, with a high contribution of imazalil
57 and dithiocarbamate. Since the concentrations provided by the different countries were merged
58 in the scenario using merged concentration data, differences between countries result from
59 differences in food consumption behaviours. These results support the approach that using
60 merged concentration data to estimate exposures in Europe seems to be realistic, as foods are
61 traded across European borders. The originality of the proposed approach was to start from a
62 CAG and to integrate information from combined exposures to identify a refined list of mixtures
63 with fewer components. As this approach was sensitive to the input data and required significant
64 resources, efforts should continue regarding data collection and harmonisation among the
65 different aspects within the pesticides regulatory framework, and to develop methods to group
66 substances and mixtures to characterise the risk.

67

68 **Keywords**

69 Mixture prioritization; Cumulative assessment group; Sparse non-negative matrix
70 underestimation; Relative Potency Factors; Dietary exposure and hazard

71

72 **Highlights**

73

- 74 • Mixtures were prioritized from dietary exposure and hazard data
- 75 • Acute and chronic exposure were estimated for 9 European countries
- 76 • One main pesticide mixture drives the risk related to chronic exposure and steatosis in
77 Europe
- 78 • Imazalil and dithiocarbamate contribute the most to the European pesticide mixture
79 exposure

80

80 **1. Introduction**

81

82 Through the environment and diet, on a daily basis populations are exposed to mixtures of
83 chemicals that can interact and cause health effects. Due to the complexity of mixtures, the
84 associated risk is difficult to characterise. Over the past decade, considerable efforts have been
85 made to propose concepts, methods, guidance and applications for the risk assessment of
86 mixtures (Boobis et al., 2008; EFSA, 2007, 2008; Fox et al., 2017; WHO, 2009). Given the
87 multitude of possible combinations, the question of which substances to assess together remains
88 a major challenge. One solution is to perform risk assessments for chemicals belonging to the
89 same chemical family and/or having the same mode of action. In this way, the European Food
90 Safety Authority (EFSA) proposed a hazard-wise method based on “common adverse
91 outcomes” to group pesticides into “cumulative assessment groups” (CAGs) (EFSA, 2013b;
92 Nielsen et al., 2012; RIVM et al., 2013). Four levels of criteria for grouping were defined, with
93 each higher level being more refined: target organs (level 1), specific phenotypic effects (level
94 2), mode of action (level 3), and mechanism of action (level 4). Currently, level 1 and 2 CAGs
95 have been identified in the nervous system and the thyroid for pesticides. Preliminary work has

96 been done on effects on the liver, adrenal glands, eyes, and developmental and reproductive
97 systems (EFSA, 2012; RIVM et al., 2013). Dose addition is the default hypothesis to assess the
98 risk of these CAGs, but the appropriateness of this assumption is hardly ever investigated
99 experimentally. The difficulty in cumulative risk assessment is the lack of information on
100 hazard and exposure of the substances classified into a certain CAG. Firstly, for several
101 pesticides, grouping into a certain CAG can be based on a small number of observations,
102 thereby introducing uncertainties regarding CAG membership and relative potency in
103 comparison to other substances in a CAG. Secondly, the mode and mechanism of action is
104 unknown for many substances, and this may not only hamper refinement into level 3 and level
105 4 CAGs, but also introduce uncertainties in addressing the combined effect. Because of this,
106 there is a need for greater efforts to study the modes and mechanisms of action of pesticides.
107 However, as a certain CAG can contain a high number of components, it is necessary to
108 prioritise the substances to be assessed in mixture testing. Like all risk assessments, combined
109 risk assessments to chemicals should not be based on the hazard (toxicological properties)
110 alone, but also on population exposure. Combined exposure can be estimated by combining
111 food consumption patterns of individuals in a population with occurrence levels of chemicals
112 in food. The number of combinations of compounds to which an individual in a population is
113 exposed can be large. Therefore, it is essential to develop a strategy that considers actual
114 exposure to extract the most relevant mixtures to which the population is exposed (Crépet et
115 al., 2013) as a prioritisation tool for further studies.

116 The present study is part of the EuroMix project (No. 633172, H2020-SFS-2014-2) which has
117 developed a strategy for mixture risk assessment. It proposes a prioritisation methodology
118 combining both exposure and hazard information to identify the most relevant mixtures of
119 chemicals belonging to any CAG to which European populations are exposed chronically and
120 acutely via food. The proposed approach starts from the list of substances in a defined CAG,
121 and reduces this list by using risk-based identification of co-occurring pesticides in the diet for
122 a given time frame. The mixture selection approach is based on sparse non-negative matrix
123 underapproximation (SNMU) (Gillis and Plemmons, 2013), which is a statistical method
124 making it possible to select the main mixtures. SNMU is a modified version of non-negative
125 matrix factorisation (NMF) (Lee and Seung, 2001), recently used to identify the main mixtures
126 associated with the diet (Béchaux et al., 2013; Traoré et al., 2016; Traoré et al., 2018). The
127 proposed approach was implemented using the web-based Monte Carlo Risk Assessment
128 (MCRA) platform, version 8.2 (Boon et al., 2015). It was applied to the level 2 CAG for liver
129 steatosis defined by EFSA (Nielsen et al., 2012; RIVM et al., 2013, 2016) and on exposure data
130 from several European countries. If needed, the identified substances in the mixtures and their
131 individual components will be further studied using several *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests. The results
132 of these additional tests may provide a more precise picture of the potency and the mode of
133 action of each substance. The mixture of substances will also be tested *in vitro* and *in vivo* to
134 refine the assumptions made on the dose- and/or response addition. The aim of our study was
135 to describe the mixture selection procedure and the identified priority mixtures for further
136 testing. The results we obtained aim to facilitate a cost-effective test procedure.

137 2. Materials and methods

138 2.1 Exposure and hazard data to identify mixtures

139 The proposed method is based on a combination of exposure and hazard information to define
140 mixtures. In practice it consists in 1) selecting a CAG and its level of grouping, 2) calculating
141 the exposures for each pesticide belonging to the selected CAG by combining quantities of
142 consumed food with the substance concentrations in those foods, 3) converting the exposure of
143 each substance to the toxicity equivalent value of the substance of reference for the selected
144 CAG, and 4) applying statistical methods to the converted exposures to determine the main
145 mixtures to which the studied population is exposed.

146 2.2 Data

147 2.2.1 Hazard data

148 The CAG for liver effects was chosen for the specific steatosis effect (second level of liver
149 toxicity). The list of pesticides in this CAG with their corresponding NOAEL and/or LOAEL
150 was established from three reports supported by EFSA (Nielsen et al., 2012; RIVM et al., 2013,
151 2016) and their associated database. The underlying studies were critically evaluated regarding
152 the following criteria, which yielded a total of 155 substances:

- 153 • All repeated-dose (short-term and long-term) toxicology studies based on oral
154 administration (diet, gavage, capsule) at the NOAELs/LOAELs were taken into
155 consideration.
- 156 • Inhalation studies were considered only for pesticides that are gasses and that could
157 therefore not be toxicologically tested via the oral route.
- 158 • Studies by the dermal route were not reported, except for substances for which no data
159 were available concerning the oral route.
- 160 • Acute LD₅₀ studies were not considered.
- 161 • *In vitro* studies were considered for information on the mechanism/mode of action only.
- 162 • Studies performed with metabolites were not included, except when the metabolite itself
163 was used in the toxicity studies instead of the parent compound due to its high instability.
- 164 • In the particular case where the active substance consists of isomer mixtures, the studies
165 performed with the racemic mixture and those carried out with the different isomers were
166 reported.
- 167 • When different isomers and/or variants were considered to be toxicologically equivalent,
168 the same specific effect was applied and the studies were reported only once.

169
170 Substances were coded using the ParamCodes from the harmonised European Standard Sample
171 Description 1 format SDD1 (EFSA, 2010). Substances were removed if no ParamCode coding
172 for pesticides, no NOAL or no LOAEL (copper compounds) were available. Some substances
173 sharing the same residue definition (benalaxyl-M and benalaxyl, cypermethrin and alpha-

174 cypermethrin, metam and dazomet, metalaxyl-M and metalaxyl, triadimefon and triadimenol)
175 were presented together in the database. This approach resulted in a total of 144 pesticides.
176 Relative potency factors (RPFs) were calculated to express the potency of each substance in the
177 CAG relative to a selected reference compound chosen based on the following criteria:

- 178 • Considering that longer-term studies (i.e. 12, 18 and 24 months) were generally performed
179 using lower concentrations compared to shorter-term studies (i.e. 28 or 90 days), priority
180 was given to long-term studies.
- 181 • Compounds characterised by an NOAEL causing fatty changes (steatosis) between 0 and
182 1 mg/kg bw/day, were first selected (to avoid the selection of an index compound eliciting
183 other organ and/or different liver effects at doses lower than those eliciting fatty changes).
- 184 • The second step in selection was made on the basis of the LOAEL/NOAEL ratio (between
185 1 and 5) to avoid dose-spacing uncertainties.
- 186 • The third step in selection was made taking into consideration only those compounds also
187 causing cell degeneration/cell alteration or cell death at similar or higher doses.
- 188 • As a final step, the compound with more studies showing liver effects was chosen as the
189 reference compound.

190 The minimum required data set for calculation of potency was a well-performed chronic study
191 with a dose-range that could provide a LOAEL for steatosis. The more studies available, the
192 extent to which the above mentioned criteria could be applied to select the NOAEL or LOAEL
193 of a particular substance to calculate its potency.

194
195 Flusilazole complying with the above criteria was selected as the reference compound. Data
196 came from 4 long term studies where liver effects were evident and LOAEL/NOAEL ratio for
197 fatty changes spaced between 2 and 5. Its NOAEL for fatty changes was of 0.53 mg/kg bw/day.
198 For each compound, the NOAEL of flusilazole was divided by the NOAEL of the particular
199 compound, which yielded the RPF. When no NOAEL was available, the LOAEL divided by
200 three was used as an assumption of the NOAEL. The RPFs make it possible to convert exposure
201 to the substances into the “toxicity unit” of the reference compound, and thus to compare the
202 exposure levels between substances within a CAG.

203 **2.2.2 Consumption data**

204 Food consumption data from the different countries were coded according to the harmonised
205 FoodEx1 coding system (EFSA, 2011). FoodEx1 is a hierarchical system based on 20 main
206 food categories divided into subgroups up to a maximum of 4 levels. For example, chocolate
207 cake is given a numerical code responding to ‘grain and grain-based products’ at level 1, to
208 ‘fine bakery wares’ at level 2, to ‘pastries and cakes’ at level 3, and to ‘chocolate cake’ at level
209 4. The age and body weight were also available for each individual. It was decided to focus on
210 the adult population aged between 18 and 64 years, and for countries where data were available,
211 on the paediatric population aged between 11 and 15 years, as these were the age ranges shared
212 by the largest number of different country surveys. A summary of consumption data is shown
213 in Table 1.

214 **Belgium:** Consumption data were provided by the National Institute of Public Health from a
215 consumption study conducted in 2004 by De Vriese et al. (2005). The study included 3,214
216 participants over 15 years of age who were interviewed about their consumption in a 2 x 24-
217 hour period (repeated non-consecutive 24h recall), and asked to fill in a questionnaire about
218 food frequency.

219 **Cyprus:** Consumption data were provided from a national study evaluating the frequency of
220 eating disorder cases (Cyprus study on eating disorders among high school students called
221 “Child Health”), which was conducted in 2003. In this study, food consumption data were
222 collected for 303 children, aged between 11 to 15 years, using a 3-day estimated dietary record.
223 No data were collected in the adult population. Most, but not all, dietary records were collected
224 over consecutive days. Amounts consumed were estimated using food package sizes and
225 household measures (e.g. cups and spoons). The consumed quantities of 1,043 food items were
226 collected.

227 **Czech Republic:** Consumption data were provided by the National Institute of Public Health.
228 They are from the national food consumption survey named SISP04 (Ruprich et al., 2006).
229 Food consumption data were collected in 2003 and 2004 for 2,590 individuals representing the
230 entire country, both genders and ages 4 to 90 years. This study used a 2 x 24h recall design
231 (with non-correlated days D1 and D2 separated by more than 14 days). The face-to-face method
232 was used for data collection. Reported data on food types were aggregated into 514 groups.

233 **Denmark:** Consumption data were provided by the Division of Risk Assessment and Nutrition
234 at the National Food Institute. The data were collected as part of DANSDA (DAnish National
235 Survey of Diet and physical Activity) 2005–2008, and constitute a subset of the data reported
236 in “Dietary habits in Denmark 2003–2008” (Pedersen et al., 2010). Food consumption data
237 were recorded concerning 2,700 Danish consumers aged 4 to 75 years. The dataset records food
238 and beverages consumed over 7 consecutive days. The individuals were drawn as a simple
239 random sample from the general population registration system. DANSDA used a 7-day pre-
240 coded (semi-closed) food diary with answering categories for the most commonly consumed
241 foods and drinks in the Danish diet. Data on a total of 414 food items were collected.

242 **France:** Consumption data were drawn from the second “Individual and National Study on
243 Food Consumption” (INCA2) carried out by the French Agency for Food, Environmental and
244 Occupational Health and Safety between late 2005 and April 2007. Two independent random
245 samples were included in this survey: 1,455 children aged between 3 to 17 years (Lioret et al.,
246 2010) and 2,624 adults aged between 18 to 79 years (Dubuisson et al., 2010). Participants were
247 selected using a three-stage random design stratified by region of residence, size of urban area,
248 and population group (adults and children). Subjects completed a 7-day food record diary and
249 portion sizes were estimated through photographs compiled in a manual adapted from the Su-
250 Vi-Max photographic booklet (Hercberg et al., 1994). The consumed quantities of 1,280 food
251 items per day were collected.

252 **Greece:** Food consumption data were obtained from 10 surveys (Crete Region) conducted by
253 the University of Crete, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Preventive Medicine and Nutrition
254 between 1988 and 2004 (Bertsias et al., 2003; Kafatos et al., 1991; Linardakis et al., 2008;
255 Moschandreas and Kafatos, 1999; University of Crete, March 2016; Xatzis et al., 2004). In
256 total, the surveys covered the dietary habits of 1,640 adults aged between 18 to 94 years and
257 528 children aged between 11 and 15 years living in Crete. The consumed quantities of

258 approximately 72 food items per day were collected. Dietary consumption was measured using
259 the 24-h recall method.

260 **Netherlands:** Food consumption data were obtained from two surveys: the Dutch National
261 Food Consumption Survey (DNFCS)-Young children (Ocké et al., 2008), and the DNFCS
262 2007–2010 (van Rossum et al., 2011). The DNFCS-Young children survey covered the dietary
263 habits of 1,279 young children aged 2 to 6 years representatively selected from the Dutch
264 population, and was conducted in 2005 and 2006. The DNFCS 2007–2010 includes the dietary
265 habits of 3,819 people aged 7 to 69 years representatively selected from the Dutch population.
266 Dietary consumption was measured using the 24-h recall method on two non-consecutive days.
267 The survey included 1,599 food items. Results of the consumption surveys were weighted for
268 small deviations in socio-demographic characteristics in order to obtain results that are
269 representative of the Dutch population.

270
271 **Slovenia:** Food consumption data were obtained from the National Food Consumption Survey
272 (CRP 2008), provided by the National Institute of Public Health Slovenia. The survey covered
273 the period 2007–2008 with data on the individual level for 407 persons, both genders, aged
274 between 18 to 65 years. The participants were selected from the Central Register of Population
275 in Slovenia with a two-stage, stratified sample design. Dietary consumption was measured
276 using the 24-h recall method for one survey day. Consumed amounts of foods were estimated
277 using a national picture book, complemented with household measures and portions indicated
278 in standard recipes. A total of 283 food groups were recorded.

279 **Spain:** Food consumption data were provided from the Encuesta ENIDE survey (AESAN,
280 2011). Data were collected in 2011 for 3,386 individuals aged between 18 to 71 years. The
281 consumed quantities of approximately 72 food items per day were collected. Dietary
282 consumption was measured using the 24-h recall method.

283 **United Kingdom:** Food consumption data were extracted from the National Diet and Nutrition
284 Survey (NDNS). The survey covered the period from July 2000 to June 2001 and included
285 1,724 adult respondents aged 19 to 64 years. After an initial face-to-face interview (CAPI
286 method), the participants recorded dietary consumption in a 7-day consecutive diary
287 (Henderson et al., 2002). A total of 490 food items were recorded.

288 **2.2.3 Concentration data**

289 Concentration data in food and drinking water were obtained from annual control and
290 monitoring programmes between 2010 and 2014 for the countries for which this was available
291 (Table 1). Data comprise pesticides levels measured in raw agricultural commodities and/or
292 food as consumed (e.g. juices). Samples obtained by objective or selective sampling were
293 included, whereas samples obtained by less formal sampling strategies were excluded since
294 they are not representative of the market. A zero value was attributed to analytical results
295 reported as below the limit of detection (LOD), following the optimistic basic scenario included
296 in guidance from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, 2012). A merged dataset was
297 created by combining data from all countries. The merged data set contained 127 pesticides in
298 the steatosis CAG, of which 93 pesticides had at least one sample above the LOD. This resulted
299 in 3,161,615 analyses applied to 204 raw agricultural food commodities, from which 0.72% of

300 measurements were quantified. For two countries, Spain and the United Kingdom, access to
301 specific national monitoring programmes for concentrations of substances was not available.

302 **Belgium:** Concentration data on pesticides were collected between 2011 and 2014, as per the
303 national monitoring programme on pesticides. The monitoring was carried out by the National
304 Institute for Food Safety (FAVV/AFSCA). The datasets contain a total of $n = 101,319$ samples,
305 of which 1,141 (1.12%) were positive detections of 135 different compounds in 112 raw
306 agricultural commodities. 115 pesticides were classified in the steatosis CAG and out of these,
307 39 had at least one sample above the LOD. 0.87% of pesticides were quantified in the CAG.

308 **Cyprus:** Concentration data were collected between 2011 and 2014 as part of the national
309 monitoring programmes. The dataset contained analytical results for up to 346 pesticides out of
310 which 81 were classified in the steatosis CAG. A total of 48 of these pesticides had at least one
311 sample above the LOD. This resulted in 124,599 analyses, of which 0.72% quantified values in
312 68 raw agricultural commodities.

313 **Czech Republic:** Concentration data generated between 2011 and 2014 were obtained from
314 the national database of analytical results for food monitoring. From the 58 substances analysed,
315 42 pesticides were selected as relevant for the steatosis CAG, and 37 pesticides had at least one
316 sample above the LOD. This resulted in 153,696 measurements in 114 raw agricultural
317 commodities, for which 1.35% were quantified.

318 **Denmark:** Data were collected between 2011 and 2014 by the Danish Veterinary and Food
319 Administration and represented commodities sold on the Danish market. The dataset contained
320 analytical results for up to 280 pesticides. Among them, 95 were included in the steatosis CAG,
321 and 58 pesticides had at least one sample above the LOD. In total, 503,879 measurements were
322 recorded in 190 raw agricultural food commodities, and 0.62% of them contained quantified
323 values.

324 **France:** Concentration data were collected between 2010 and 2014 by the French ministries in
325 charge of consumer affairs, agriculture and health. The monitoring programmes provided
326 analytical results for up to 194 pesticides. Among them, 120 were in the steatosis CAG, and 70
327 substances had at least one sample above the LOD. This represented 907,565 measurements in
328 153 raw agricultural food commodities, of which 0.53% were quantified.

329 **Greece:** Pesticide residue data were provided by the Hellenic Ministry of Rural Development
330 and Food (Department of Plant Protection Products & Biocides) for the period between 2010
331 and 2014. Among the analysed pesticides, 91 pesticides were relevant for the steatosis CAG,
332 and 56 pesticides had at least one sample above the LOD. This represented 324,561
333 measurements and 0.65% were quantified in 68 raw agricultural food commodities.

334 **Netherlands:** Concentration data were collected between 2010 and 2013. The dataset contained
335 analytical results for 665 pesticides, of which 110 were included in the steatosis CAG. In all,
336 67 pesticides had at least one sample above the LOD. This resulted in 643,538 analyses with
337 0.89% quantified values in 131 raw agricultural food commodities.

338 **Slovenia:** Slovenian concentration data were collected between 2011 and 2014 by the Ministry
339 of Agriculture, Forestry and Food. Among the 109 pesticides analysed, 87 belonged to the
340 steatosis CAG, and 40 pesticides had at least one sample above the LOD. The dataset contained
341 109,810 analyses with 0.49% quantified values in 70 raw agricultural food commodities.

342 **2.2.4 Data matching**

343 **Matching concentration and consumption data:** All data were uploaded into the MCRA
344 software. To match food consumption data with concentration data in raw agricultural products,
345 a conversion table was used (Boon et al., 2015). This conversion table is based on Dutch recipes
346 and contains conversion factors to convert foods classified according to FoodEx1 to their edible
347 raw agricultural commodity (RAC) ingredients (e.g. an apple pie is broken down in its mass
348 percentage of apple, flour, butter, sugar and eggs, or the mass percentage of raw spinach to
349 obtain 100 g of cooked spinach) The conversion table included information on important
350 processing steps, such as cooking, milling and juicing. Processing factors from the German
351 *Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung* (BfR; accessed on 1 September 2015) were used to account
352 for the effect of these processing steps on exposure levels. For 46 out of the 144 pesticides,
353 processing factors were available.

354 **Matching hazard and exposure data:** Pesticides in the CAG lists from EFSA and DTU are
355 given as parent compounds rather than residues, whereas concentration data were mostly
356 expressed as residue definitions for enforcement, which can be a single parent compound, one
357 or more metabolites (i.e. pesticide metabolites in plants or animals), or a combination of the
358 parent compound and metabolites. To match the parent compounds in the CAG to the
359 concentration data, the SSD1 ParamCodes for current residue definitions were obtained from
360 the pesticides database of the European Commission; these are the residue definitions for
361 enforcement. It should be noted that according to the EFSA Opinion of 2012, residue definitions
362 for risk assessment should be used rather than residue definitions for enforcement. The residue
363 definition for risk assessment can be obtained by applying conversion factors to concentrations
364 obtained from the residue definition for enforcement. For simplicity, these conversion factors
365 were assumed to be 1.

366 **2.3 Exposure calculation and scenarios**

367 The optimistic basic approach of EFSA (2012) implemented in the MCRA software was
368 followed to calculate both chronic (long-term) and acute (short-term) exposure. Under this
369 approach, values lower than the LOD as well as missing values were set to 0. The empirical
370 distributions were used for concentration data and processing factors were applied to integrate
371 the effect of process on concentration levels. No between-lot and sample variability factors were
372 considered. In the chronic scenario, the mean of available concentration values per
373 pesticide/food combination was multiplied by the mean of consumed food quantity on the
374 different recorded days for each individual, which is the simple Observed Individual Means
375 (OIM) model (EFSA, 2012). In the acute scenario, concentration values and individual-days of
376 consumption were randomly selected by Monte Carlo simulations in their empirical
377 distributions to produce individual-day exposure to each pesticide.

378 Therefore, exposure per day was calculated by multiplying the consumed quantities per food
379 for each individual by the concentrations of the different substances in this food, following the
380 chronic and acute scenarios. Then, the exposures from the different foods for each substance
381 were summed, divided by the body weight of each individual, and multiplied by the relative
382 potency factors RPF:

383

$$E_{ijs} = \frac{\sum_{f=1}^F q_{ijf} c_{ijfs}}{bw_i} \times RPF_s$$

384 where E_{ijs} is the exposure to substance s by individual i on day j (in microgram substance per
 385 kg body weight), q_{ijf} is the consumed quantity of food f (in g) by the individual i on day j , c_{ijfs}
 386 is the concentration of substance s in food f eaten by individual i on day j (in mg/kg), and bw_i
 387 is the body weight of individual i (in kg). F is the number of foods in which the substance is
 388 present. Note that all exposures are zero or positive values.

389

390 Four exposure scenarios were tested and compared:

- 391 1. Chronic exposure calculated with the merged concentration dataset for the adult population
 392 (18-64 years).
- 393 2. Chronic exposure calculated with the country-specific concentration datasets for the adult
 394 population (18-64 years).
- 395 3. Acute exposure calculated with the merged concentration dataset for the adult population
 396 (18-64 years).
- 397 4. Chronic exposure calculated with the merged concentration dataset for children aged
 398 between 11 and 15 years.

399 2.4 Mixture selection method

400 The method used to extract the mixtures from the matrix of exposures E is based on the sparse
 401 non-negative matrix underestimation (SNMU) model (Gillis and Plemmons, 2013). The SNMU
 402 can be described as a method that finds a representation of the data in a lower dimension. The
 403 SNMU solution approximates the non-negative input matrix (i.e. the exposure matrix E) by two
 404 non-negative matrices (U and V) with lower dimension k , such that the product of the two is as
 405 close as possible to the original input matrix (Figure 1). k represents the pre-set number of
 406 mixtures. The matrix U contains weights (SNMU weight) of pesticides per mixture, the matrix
 407 V contains the coefficients of the presence of the mixture per individual or exposure day, and
 408 ϵ is the matrix of residuals due to the approximation. The matrices U , V and ϵ were obtained
 409 by minimising the criterion: $\|E - UV\|^2$ such that $U \geq 0$ and $V \geq 0$.

410

411 **Figure 1: SNMU decomposition of exposure data.** The exposure matrix E with dimensions s (number of pesticides)
 412 and n (number of individuals for chronic or exposure days for acute exposure) is approximated by matrix U and V with
 413 dimensions $(s \times k)$ and $(k \times n)$ respectively, where k represents the number of mixtures.

414 The non-zero entries in each column of U indicate the components of the selected mixtures.
415 The higher the SNMU weight, the higher the participation of the substance to the mixture. In a
416 technical sense, a mixture, as defined from the non-zero elements of a column of matrix U,
417 could be composed of just one substance. In order to avoid solutions with only or mostly single-
418 substance ‘mixtures’, the method was adapted by first using the maximum cumulative ratio
419 (MCR, Price and Han (2011)) to restrict the columns of E to only cases where mixtures are
420 important, in order to focus on the individuals (or the individual-days for acute cases) with
421 exposure profiles composed of multiple substances. The MCR is defined as the ratio of the
422 cumulative exposure received by an individual to the largest exposure contribution from a
423 single compound:

$$\text{MCR} = \text{cumulative exposure} / \text{maximum exposure from a single compound}$$

424
425 If the MCR is large, it is important to consider cumulative effects, if the MCR is close to 1, the
426 individual exposure (or individual-days) will not differ extensively from a single-compound
427 assessment. Only individuals (or individual-days) with an MCR above a chosen threshold were
428 used for the SNMU mixture selection. It was decided to work on the 5% exposures with the
429 highest MCR values. The SMNU and MCR methods were implemented in MCRA software.

430 **3. Results**

431 Selection of pesticide mixtures was carried out for each of the nine countries following the four
432 exposure scenarios and considering at most three mixtures ($k=3$). For acute exposure, it was
433 necessary to select highly co-exposed individuals. For chronic exposure, the three mixtures
434 explained between 95% and 100% of the total variance in each of the countries and exposure
435 scenarios. For acute exposure, the variance explained by the three mixtures ranged between
436 41% and 75%. Irrespective of the exposure scenario and the country, the first mixture was the
437 one that explained the higher percentage of variance: at least 55.1% for the chronic scenarios,
438 and 16.2% for the acute scenario. Results are detailed below for this first main mixture.

439 **3.1. Mixture components across the scenarios and countries**

440 Looking at all countries, the main pesticides in the first selected mixture that contributed to
441 population exposure were similar across scenarios (Table 2). In particular, seven compounds
442 were observed in almost all scenarios: imazalil, dithiocarbamates, carbendazim and benomyl,
443 cypermethrin, thiacloprid and deltamethrin, and triadimefon and triadimenol. Among these
444 compounds, two pesticides, imazalil and dithiocarbamates, were observed in almost all
445 countries and contributed the most to the mixture in comparison to the other substances. For
446 the first scenario (adult, chronic, merged data), imazalil and dithiocarbamates were observed
447 with an SNMU weight of 85% and 13% for Belgium and the Netherlands, 72% and 23% for
448 Denmark, and 72% and 24% for France, respectively. Imazalil and dithiocarbamates were also
449 observed as major components for the scenario in “children, chronic, merged data”. Regarding
450 the scenarios with country-specific data, imazalil was found to be the main pesticide, followed
451 by dithiocarbamates for Belgium, Denmark, France, and the Netherlands.

452 The seven compounds with the highest participation to the mixture were confirmed by high
453 contributions of these substances to the total exposure (Figure 2). Imazalil contributed most to

454 the mixture for all countries and scenarios, and may lead to 75% of the total exposure for the
455 adult population with chronic exposure and merged concentration data in the Czech Republic.
456 In fact, regarding exposure levels, imazalil was the compound with the highest exposure levels.
457 The highest value of P95 exposure to imazalil was observed for the Netherlands, in the scenario
458 on chronic exposure in adults using country-specific data with a value of 7.25 µg/kg bw/day
459 contributing to 57% of the total exposure. Another high P95 exposure of 7.15 µg/kg bw/day
460 was observed in the paediatric population for Cyprus, which contributed 67% to the total
461 exposure. For dithiocarbamates, the second major contributor to the mixture, the highest values
462 of P95 exposure were also observed for the Netherlands, in the scenario on chronic exposure
463 for adults with specific concentration data at 0.77 µg/kg bw/day, contributing 33% of the total
464 exposure, followed by the P95 exposure of Slovenia and Spain, in the scenario on chronic
465 exposure in adults with merged concentration data (e.g. 0.76 and 0.72 µg/kg bw/day
466 respectively, contributing 48% and 34% of the total exposure).
467 Greece had slightly different results. Imazalil was not observed in the mixture found for the
468 chronic adult exposure scenario with merged and specific data. The substances that contributed
469 the most to the mixture were dithiocarbamates, with an SNMU weight of 95% and a
470 contribution to total exposure of 56% for merged data in adults, and 90% and 64% for specific
471 data in adults. For the children scenario, dithiocarbamates were in the first position (78%)
472 followed by cypermethrin (9%) and imazalil (6%).
473 Looking at the different scenarios, the contributions of compounds for the whole population
474 were generally lower for the acute scenario. Thus, except for Greece, where imazalil highly
475 contributed with a SNMU weight of 92% and a contribution to total exposure of 19%, imazalil
476 contributed less to the mixture in acute exposure. Furthermore, the SNMU weights of
477 triadimefon and triadimenol were significantly higher in the mixture with acute exposure and
478 reached an SNMU weight of 42% in Slovenia.
479 Some compounds were observed only in one scenario for Greece and the Czech Republic.
480 Abamectin and ethoprophos were observed in Greece only for the chronic scenario with specific
481 national concentration data in the adult population, but the contribution of these compounds to
482 the mixture was relatively low (e.g. SNMU weight of 1%). Furthermore, for this country, in the
483 child population, the mixture contained metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M, which were only observed
484 in this case (e.g. SNMU weight of 1%). The compound flufenoxuron was observed in Greece
485 only for chronic exposure in the adult population, with country-specific concentration data and
486 in the paediatric population with merged data. For the Czech Republic, fluazinam was observed
487 only in the chronic adult exposure scenario with specific concentration data (e.g. SNMU weight
488 of 0.05%) and iprodione in the acute exposure scenario (SNMU weight of 1%). These
489 compounds in combination contribute less than 10% to total exposure.
490
491 Concerning other mixtures and considering the first scenario (adult chronic and merged data)
492 for France, Spain and Greece, mixtures 2 and 3 were composed of the same 7 compounds found
493 for the first mixture but with a different order of importance. For example, in France mixture 2
494 compounds and their SNMU weights were: dithiocarbamates (93%), cypermethrin (3%),
495 carbendazim and benomyl (2%), triadimefon and triadimenol (1%), deltamethrin (1%),
496 thiacloprid (1%). The last two compounds were not present in the first French mixture. Imazalil

497 was not present in the second mixture but found alone (SNMU weight of 100%) in the third
498 mixture.

499 For Denmark, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Slovenia and the Czech Republic
500 considering the first scenario (adult chronic merged data), new compounds were found in
501 addition to those found in the first mixture. Their SNMU weights were equal to 1% each:
502 dicofol, acetamiprid, iprodione, tebuconazole, fenbuconazole, flufenoxuron, deltamethrin,
503 dithiocarbamates, fipronil, and iprovalicarb. Similar results were found for the other scenarios.

504 **3.2 Contribution of food pesticides to the total population exposure**

505 Table 3 shows the proportion of the different food/pesticide combinations where the SNMU
506 weight of the mixture was relatively high (higher than 5%) contributing the most to the mixture
507 in chronic and acute cases. Imazalil and dithiocarbamates are the major compounds found in
508 food for both chronic and acute exposure. For chronic exposure, imazalil was mainly recorded
509 in oranges and grapefruits in many countries, and at a lower level in mandarins for Belgium
510 and the Czech Republic. For acute exposure, imazalil was also mainly observed in oranges,
511 mandarins, grapefruit, but also in bananas, lemons, limes and pears.

512 However, dithiocarbamates were not observed in the same foods following the different
513 exposure scenarios. For chronic exposure, dithiocarbamates were mainly observed in cultivated
514 mushrooms in Belgium, the Czech Republic, France, the Netherlands, Spain and the United
515 Kingdom, but not in Greece where cucumbers formed an important part of exposure (e.g. 21.4%
516 of the total measurements), and wine grapes for the Czech Republic (e.g. 4.2%). For acute
517 exposure, dithiocarbamates were mainly observed in lettuce, apples, wine grapes, tomatoes, and
518 pears in several countries, but also in cucumbers for Greece (e.g. 15.9%).

519 A high contribution of triadimefon and triadimenol to exposure was also recorded for
520 pineapples for acute exposure and especially in Spain (e.g. 12.5% in acute exposure).
521 Cypermethrin was mainly recorded in wheat in many countries, but in Greece, cocoa (fermented
522 beans) was the main source of exposure to cypermethrin (e.g. 19.9%).

523

524

525

526 **Figure 2. Cumulative contribution (%) of the different substances** in each country for the four scenarios: 1.

527 Adults, chronic exposure and merged concentration data; 2. Adults, chronic exposure and specific concentration

528 data; 3. Adults, acute exposure and merged concentration data; 4. Children, chronic exposure and merged

529 concentration data.

530

531

532 **Figure 2. Cumulative contribution (%) of the different substances** in each country for the four scenarios: 1.
 533 Adults, chronic exposure and merged concentration data; 2. Adults, chronic exposure and specific concentration
 534 data; 3. Adults, acute exposure and merged concentration data; 4. Children, chronic exposure and merged
 535 concentration data.

Table 1. Description of consumption and concentration data for nine different European countries. n total = number of individuals in the overall consumption survey, n=number of individuals included in this study (adults 18–64 years old, children 11–15 years old), N= number of substances in steatosis CAG after matching with contamination data; the number in brackets indicates the number of substances with measurements \geq LOD. No national monitoring data was available for Spain (SP) and the United Kingdom (UK)

Country	Consumption survey				Consumption data used for the study				National concentration survey			
	Method	Years	Name	Population	n total	Mean age (min / max values)	Weight mean (min /max values)	n	Years	N	Number of measurements	Percent of measurements \geq LOD in total measurements
Belgium (BE)	2 x 24 h recall	2004	Diet National 2004	Adults (14-105 years)	3214	40 (18-64)	71.4 (39-133)	1356	2011-2014	115 (39)	393 967	0.87
Cyprus (CY)	3-d record	2003	Child Health	Children (11-15 years)	303	12.8 (11-15)	54.0 (27-144)	303	2011-2014	81 (48)	124 599	0.72%
Czech Republic (CZ)	2 x 24 h recall	2003-2004	SISP04	Adults (18-64 years)	1666	43.0 (18-64)	75.8 (43-183)	1666	2011-2014	42 (37)	153 696	1.35%
				Children (11-14 years)	109	12.3 (11-14)	46.1 (27-83)	109				
Denmark (DK)	7-d record	2003–2008	DANSDA 2005-08	Adults (18-79 years)	1990	43.0 (18-64)	75.8 (43-183)	1710	2011-2014	95 (58)	503 879	0.62%
				Children (4-17 years)	710	12.7 (11-15)	52.3 (28-100)	234				
France (FR)	7-d record	2005–2007	INCA2	Adults (18-79 years)	2624	40.6 (18-64)	70.6 (35-171)	2276	2010-2014	120 (70)	907 565	0.53%
				Children (3-17 years)	1455	13.1 (11-15)	49.5 (25-128)	585				
Greece (GR)	3-d record	1988-2004	Regional Crete	Adults (18-94 years)	1640	33.2 (18-64)	72.9 (40-141)	1585	2010-2014	91 (56)	324 561	0.65%
				Children (11-15 years)	528	13.4 (11-15)	55.3 (26-109)	528				
Netherland (NL)	2 x 24 h recall	2007-2010	VCP-Basic	Adults (18-69 years)	2230	41.5 (18-64)	80.3 (39-192)	2056	2010-2013	110 (67)	643 538	0.89%
		2005-2006	VCP-Kids	Children (7-17 years)	1589	13.0 (11-15)	52.5 (27-116)	727				
				Children (2-6 years)	1279							
Slovenia (SI)	24 h recall	2007-2008	CRP 2008	Adults (18-65 years)	407	41.4 (18-64)	74.5 (44-125)	400	2012 - 2014	87 (40)	109 810	0.49%
Spain (SP)	3-d record	2011	Encuesta ENIDE	Adults (18-71 years)	3386	39.4 (18-64)	68.5 (41-140)	3371				
United Kingdom (UK)	7-d record	2000-2001	NDNS	Adults (19-64 years)	1724	40.6 (19-64)	76.3 (39-200)	1724				

Table 2. Characteristics of the exposure estimates (mean, median, P5 and P95 in µg/kg bw/day), SNMU weights and contributions to the total exposure for the main mixture following the four scenarios in each country.

Name compound	RPF	Belgium (BE)						Czech Republic (CZ)						Cyprus (CY)						
		SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	
Scenario 1 (Adults, chronic, merged)		1356 individuals. Variance: 75.6%						1666 individuals. Variance: 63.7%.												
	Imazalil	0.13	85%	44%	0.98	0.22	0	3.80	65%	31%	0.41	0.09	0.002	1.1						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	13%	39%	0.22	0.17	0.02	0.53	25%	39%	0.13	0.09	0.016	0.35						
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	1%	2%	0.03	0.02	0.002	0.10	2%	4%	0.03	0.02	0.003	0.08						
	Cypermethrin	0.28	1%	4%	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.09	3%	8%	0.05	0.04	0.013	0.12						
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							2%	4%	0.01	0.002	0	0.06						
	Thiacloprid	0.44							2%	4%	0.01	0.005	0.001	0.06						
Deltamethrin	0.53							1%	4%	0.01	0.008	0.002	0.04							
Scenario 2 (Adults, chronic, specific)		1356 individuals. Variance: 95.9%						756 individuals. Variance: 99.3%.												
	Imazalil	0.13	91%	66%	1.54	0.27	0	5.91	99%	75%	0.25	0.05	0.001	1.11						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	9%	16%	0.09	0.07	0.01	0.24												
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2																		
	Cypermethrin	0.28																		
	Thiacloprid	0.44							0.5%	4%	0.004	0.002	0	0.01						
	Abamectin	2.1																		
	Deltamethrin	0.53																		
	Ethoprophos	21																		
	Fluazinam	0.13							0.5%	5%	0.02	0.007	0	0.06						
Flufenoxuron	2.3																			
Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59																			
Scenario 3 (Adults,		2445 exposure days. Variance: 35.5%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population						1629 exposure days. Variance: 60.5%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population												

acute, merged)	Imazalil	0.13	54%	64%	0.84	0.007	0	5.09	46%	22%	0.07	0.007	0	0.68							
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53							12%	12%	0.02	0.003	0	0.1506							
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59	38%	7%	0.02	0	0	0.05	20%	13%	0.02	0.002	0	0.12							
	Cypermethrin	0.28	5%	5%	0.03	0	0	0.11	3%	8%	0.01	0.001	0	0.07							
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	3%	3%	0.03	0	0	0.09	4%	7%	0.02	0.001	0	0.07							
	Thiacloprid	0.44							12%	11%	0.01	0.001	0	0.11							
	Tebuconazole	0.09							1%	2%	0.01	0.002	0	0.09							
	Deltamethrin	0.53							1%	3%	0.003	0	0	0.01							
	Iprodione	0.005							1%	1%	0.14	0.02	0	0.87							
Scenario 4 (Children, chronic, merged)	Imazalil	0.13							109 individuals. Variance: 83.8%				303 individuals. Variance: 96.9%								
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53							75%	40%	0.9	0.36	0.002	1.3	88%	67%	2.43	1.78	0.001	7.15	
	Cypermethrin	0.28							16%	30%	0.17	0.14	0.034	0.41	11%	20%	0.18	0.15	0.045	0.39	
	Thiacloprid	0.44							2%	6%	0.07	0.06	0.021	0.16	1%	3%	0.05	0.04	0.014	0.1	
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2							2%	4%	0.03	0.01	0.001	0.12							
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							1%	3%	0.04	0.03	0.004	0.11							
	Metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M	0.06							2%	5%	0.02	0.01	0.0004	0.1							
	Deltamethrin	0.53																			
	Flufenoxuron	2.3																			

Table 2. Continuation of the table.

Name compound	RPF	Denmark (DK)							France (FR)						Greece (GR)					
		SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	
Scenario 1 (Adults, chronic, merged)		1710 individuals. Variance: 83.5%							2276 individuals. Variance: 71.6%						1785 individuals. Variance: 83.0%					
	Imazalil	0.13	72%	45%	1.03	0.67	0.022	3.35	72%	39%	0.87	0.45	0.004	2.97						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	23%	37%	0.21	0.19	0.057	0.45	24%	43%	0.24	0.19	0.038	0.57	95%	56%	0.06	0.003	0	0.32
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.20	1%	2%	0.03	0.03	0.007	0.07	1%	2%	0.03	0.02	0.004	0.08	2%	3%	0.007	0.002	0	0.03
	Cypermethrin	0.28	2%	4%	0.04	0.04	0.014	0.08	2%	4%	0.04	0.03	0.013	0.08	1%	13%	0.03	0.02	0.002	0.07
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							1%	3%	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.06	1%	2%	0.002	0.001	0	0.01
	Thiacloprid	0.44	1%	2%	0.02	0.01	0.002	0.04												
Deltamethrin	0.53																			
Scenario 2 (Adults, chronic, specific)		1710 individuals. Variance: 95.8%							2276 individuals. Variance: 77.2%						1585 individuals. Variance: 93.6%					
	Imazalil	0.13	90%	64%	0.79	0.51	0.016	2.53	84%	46%	0.75	0.41	0.003	2.53						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	9%	22%	0.07	0.06	0.015	0.16	12%	34%	0.14	0.11	0.008	0.35	90%	64%	0.07	0.003	0	0.42
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.20	1%	3%	0.02	0.02	0.005	0.05	1%	2%	0.02	0.02	0.003	0.05	2%	5%	0.01	0	0	0.07
	Cypermethrin	0.28							1%	4%	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.06	2%	4%	0.007	0	0	0.04
	Thiacloprid	0.44																		
	Abamectin	2.10													1%	2%	0.0004	0	0	0.004
	Deltamethrin	0.53							1%	4%	0.02	0.01	0.001	0.05						
	Ethoprophos	21.00													2%	3%	0.001	0	0	0.001
	Fluazinam	0.13																		
	Flufenoxuron	2.30													3%	4%	0.001	0.002	0	0.006
Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							1%	4%	0.01	0.006	0	0.05							

			8917 exposure days. Variance: 33.8%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population						9451 exposure days. Variance: 42.1%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population						4635 exposure days. Variance: 16.2%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population					
Scenario 3 (Adults, acute, merged)	Imazalil	0.13	37%	9%	0.03	0.008	0.001	0.06	49%	26%	0.15	0.006	0	0.78	92%	19%	0.05	0	0	0.08
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	42%	3%	0.005	0.004	0.002	0.007	51%	14%	0.02	0	0	0.08						
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59	3%	10%	0.01	0.004	0	0.04												
	Cypermethrin	0.28													5%	25%	0.03	0.01	0	0.09
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.20																		
	Thiacloprid	0.44	18%	9%	0.006	0.002	0	0.04							1%	2%	0.002	0	0	0.001
	Tebuconazole	0.09																		
	Deltamethrin	0.53																		
	Iprodione	0.005																		
Scenario 4 (Children, chronic, merged)	Imazalil	0.13	234 individuals. Variance: 95.3%						585 individuals. Variance: 88%						5328 individuals. Variance : 56.3%					
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	79%	57%	1.71	1.07	0.053	4.84	84%	54%	1.5	0.91	0.012	4.69	6%	6%	0.01	0	0	0.08
	Cypermethrin	0.28	17%	28%	0.21	0.18	0.060	0.39	13%	27%	0.19	0.15	0.025	0.47	78%	26%	0.01	0.001	0	0.07
	Thiacloprid	0.44	1%	3%	0.04	0.04	0.017	0.09	1%	4%	0.05	0.04	0.014	0.1	9%	41%	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.07
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.20	1%	3%	0.03	0.02	0.004	0.09							3%	2%	0.001	0	0	0.001
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59	0.6%	2%	0.03	0.03	0.007	0.07	1%	2%	0.03	0.02	0.004	0.1	2%	1%	0.002	0	0	0.01
	Metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M	0.06							1%	4%	0.03	0.01	0.001	0.11						
	Deltamethrin	0.53													1%	10%	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.08
	Flufenoxuron	2.30													1%	4%	0.002	0.001	0	0.005
														1%	1%	0.0001	0	0	0.001	

Table 2. Continuation of the table.

Name compound	RPF	Netherlands (NL)							Slovenia (SL)						Spain (SP)					
		SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	
Scenario 1 (Adults, chronic, merged)		2056 individuals. Variance: 79.8%							400 individuals. Variance: 61.8%						3371 individuals. Variance: 55.1%					
	Imazalil	0.13	85%	47%	0.99	0.31	0	4.04	82%	28%	0.76	0.1	0.0002	3.43	78%	38%	1.26	0.69	0.002	4.3
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	13%	33%	0.18	0.14	0.02	0.46	15%	48%	0.33	0.29	0.03	0.76	19%	34%	0.29	0.23	0.04	0.72
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	1%	2%	0.03	0.02	0.003	0.08	1%	2%	0.04	0.02	0.002	0.12	1%	2%	0.04	0.03	0.006	0.1
	Cypermethrin	0.28	1%	4%	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.09	1%	4%	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.13	2%	6%	0.1	0.07	0.014	0.26
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							1%	6%	0.04	0.004	0.0005	0.16						
	Thiacloprid	0.44							1%	4%	0.03	0.01	0.001	0.11						
Deltamethrin	0.53																			
Scenario 2 (Adults, chronic, specific)		2056 individuals. Variance: 87.9%							400 individuals. Variance: 66.9%											
	Imazalil	0.13	85%	57%	1.74	0.48	0	7.25	99%	34%	0.54	0.06	0	2.32						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	13%	30%	0.23	0.16	0.005	0.77												
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2																		
	Cypermethrin	0.28																		
	Thiacloprid	0.44							1%	2%	0.01	0.008	0	0.03						
	Abamectin	2.1																		
	Deltamethrin	0.53																		
	Ethoprophos	21																		
	Fluazinam	0.13																		
Flufenoxuron	2.3																			
Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59																			
Scenario 3 (Adults, acute, merged)		2878 exposure days. Variance: 45%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population							1576 exposure days. Variance: 44.8%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population						3367 exposure days. Variance: 38.7%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population					
	Imazalil	0.13	45%	17%	0.04	0.004	0	0.24	44%	22%	0.18	0.005	0	0.90	75%	22%	0.17	0.002	0	0.092

	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	8%	10%	0.006	0	0	0.03	6%	12%	0.02	0	0	0.14	6%	11%	0.02	0	0	0.13	
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59	34%	11%	0.006	0	0	0.03	42%	15%	0.03	0	0	0.16	8%	11%	0.02	0	0	0.11	
	Cypermethrin	0.28	5%	11%	0.01	0.002	0	0.05	1%	9%	0.03	0.003	0	0.19	2%	9%	0.03	0.001	0	0.18	
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	2%	9%	0.01	0.001	0	0.06	2%	7%	0.04	0.002	0	0.18	2%	7%	0.04	0.001	0	0.16	
	Thiacloprid	0.44							6%	13%	0.03	0	0	0.17	5%	12%	0.03	0	0	0.16	
	Tebuconazole	0.09	1%	3%	0.01	0.001	0	0.04							1%	4%	0.04	0.001	0	0.16	
	Deltamethrin	0.53																			
	Iprodione	0.005																			
			727 individuals. Variance: 84.2%																		
	Imazalil	0.13	87%	48%	0.95	0.15	0.001	4.35													
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	11%	30%	0.15	0.12	0.02	0.39													
	Cypermethrin	0.28	1%	5%	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.09													
Scenario 4 (Children, chronic, merged)	Thiacloprid	0.44																			
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2																			
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59																			
	Metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M	0.06																			
	Deltamethrin	0.53																			
	Flufenoxuron	2.3																			

Table 2. Continuation of the table.

Name compound	RPF	United Kingdom						
		SNMU weight	Contrib.	Mean	Median	P5	P95	
		1724 individuals. Variance: 71.6%						
Scenario 1 (Adults, chronic, merged)	Imazalil	0.13	76%	33%	0.77	0.29	0.003	2.98
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	20%	38%	0.19	0.16	0.022	0.48
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	1%	3%	0.03	0.02	0.003	0.07
	Cypermethrin	0.28	1%	5%	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.08
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59						
	Thiacloprid	0.44						
	Deltamethrin	0.53						
Scenario 2 (Adults, chronic, specific)	Imazalil	0.13						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53						
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2						
	Cypermethrin	0.28						
	Thiacloprid	0.44						
	Abamectin	2.1						
	Deltamethrin	0.53						
	Ethoprophos	21						
	Fluazinam	0.13						
	Flufenoxuron	2.3						
Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59							

			10767 exposure days. Variance: 37.5%. MCR cut-off at 5% of co-exposed population					
Scenario 3 (Adults, acute, merged)	Imazalil	0.13	85%	25%	0.10	0.005	0	0.42
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53	9%	13%	0.01	0	0	0.05
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59	2%	11%	0.01	0	0	0.03
	Cypermethrin	0.28	1%	9%	0.02	0.001	0	0.08
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2	2%	7%	0.02	0	0	0.08
	Thiacloprid	0.44						
	Tebuconazole	0.09						
	Deltamethrin	0.53						
	Iprodione	0.005						
Scenario 4 (Children, chronic, merged)	Imazalil	0.13						
	Dithiocarbamates	0.53						
	Cypermethrin	0.28						
	Thiacloprid	0.44						
	Carbendazim and benomyl	0.2						
	Triadimefon and triadimenol	0.59						
	Metalaxyl and metalaxyl-M	0.06						
	Deltamethrin	0.53						
Flufenoxuron	2.3							

Table 3. Contribution of major compounds in specific foods to cumulative exposure for all individual-days which contribute the most to the mixture exposure (at least 5%) for the adult population (18-64 years) with merged data concentration in the case of chronic and acute exposure.

Name compound	Food composition	Belgium (BE)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Denmark (DK)	France (FR)	Greece (GR)	Netherlands (NL)	Slovenia (SI)	Spain (SP)	United Kingdom (UK)
Chronic exposure										
Imazalil	Oranges	31.5%		5.3%				5.4%		23.7%
	Grapefruit	3.0%				1.9%	1.1%	1.1%		
	Mandarins	4.7%	0.4%							
Dithiocarbamates	Cultivated mushrooms	12.6%	3.6%		9.7%				6.6%	10.2%
	Cucumbers					21.4%				
	Wine grapes	7.2%	4.2%							
	Lettuce	4.3%								
	Apple	1.9%								1.1%
Acute exposure										
Imazalil	Oranges	43.9%	19.8%	45.7%	40.8%	3.2%	49.6%	16.8%	36.1%	38.9%
	Mandarins	7.3%	9.0%	11.4%	6.8%		6.4%	7.2%	5.6%	4.5%
	Grapefruit	4.4%	4.3%	1.2%	2.7%	4.9%	4.3%	5.1%	2.3%	3.9%
	Bananas	1.8%	3.7%	3.9%	1.3%		1.9%	2.1%	1.8%	3.4%
	Lemon	3.8%	6.5%		4.2%	8.4%		4.6%	1.9%	2.3%
	Limes		1.3%					2.8%		
	Pear					1.9%				
Dithiocarbamates	Lettuce	3.2%	1.3%	4.2%	7.6%		2.1%	21.3%	8.9%	6.5%
	Apple	1.0%	2.0%	2.4%	0.8%			1.2%		
	Wine grapes	1.2%	1.1%	1.5%	1.5%	4.20%				
	Tomatoes	0.7%	1.0%	0.9%	0.8%				0.7%	
	Currants (red, black, white)		0.9%					0.8%		1.0%
	Pear			1.0%		2.8%				
	Cucumbers					15.9%				
Triadimefon and triadimenol	Pineapple	6.4%	5.0%	1.4%	4.6%	1.7%	5.1%	6.8%	12.5%	4.6%
	Cucumbers					1.3%				
Cypermethrin	Wheat (spelt, triticale)	1.7%	3.2%	0.7%	1.4%		1.3%	1.8%	4.4%	1.1%
	Table grapes		0.5%					2.0%		
	Barley		2.6%	0.6%						1.1%
	Cocoa (fermented beans)					19.9%				
	Cherries								1.5%	
Thiacloprid	Currants (red, black, white)		2.3%	1.3%	0.9%			3.4%		3.4%

551 **4. Discussion**

552 The proposed approach in combining exposure levels with CAG grouping makes it
553 possible to prioritize mixtures from a large range of pesticides. Applying this method to 144
554 pesticides classified in the steatosis CAG, and following several exposure scenarios for 9
555 countries, enabled us to prioritize 15 pesticides.

556 Across the different scenarios and countries, one mixture explained the major part of the total
557 exposure. This mixture is composed of two high contributors which are imazalil and
558 dithiocarbamates. The relative potency factors (RPFs) of the two substances are relatively low
559 compared to the other substances, especially for imazalil. This implies that their presence in the
560 mixture is due to high co-exposures of the population to these pesticides, and thus to high
561 concentrations in consumed foods. In fact, imazalil and dithiocarbamates have one of the
562 highest percentages of quantified values in food (around 7%). Since the same residue
563 concentrations are used in the scenario using the merged dataset, inconsistencies between
564 countries result from variability in food consumption behaviours and/or differences between
565 the designs, the methodology, the time and the size of the consumption surveys. For most
566 countries, the principal mixtures were similar, leading to the supposition that the design of the
567 surveys had not a significant impact on mixture selection. The difference with Greece mixture
568 came from the fact that cucumbers are the main drivers of dithiocarbamates intake whereas in
569 other countries the presence of imazalil and dithiocarbamates were due to the consumption of
570 fruits and mushrooms. During the last years, EFSA tended to harmonize the design and the
571 food coding used in the food consumption surveys between the Member States of the European
572 Union (EFSA, 2014). For example in France, the dietary collection method was changed from
573 the 7-consecutive-day food record previously used in the Individual and National food
574 consumption surveys (INCA) to 3-non-consecutive day of 24-h dietary recall, completed by a
575 food propensity questionnaire for the INCA3 survey. So in future, comparison of mixtures
576 between European countries would be less impacted by methodological issues related to food
577 consumption survey design.

578 Scenarios with country-specific data lead to similar mixtures with fewer components
579 compared to the one with the merged dataset, which could be due to data gaps. These results
580 support the idea that using a merged dataset to estimate European exposures seems to be
581 realistic as foods are traded between European countries. Moreover, using merged datasets
582 makes it possible to fill data gaps for countries with lower numbers of analyses. However, using
583 merging datasets with different analytical methodologies and not weighted for
584 representativeness may introduce uncertainties in concentration. This uncertainty could be
585 reduced in future works in considering information provided in the SSD1 format regarding
586 analytical methodology, the subsequent quality assurance measures and the coverage of
587 sampled regions. Efforts must continue to harmonize and to combine data at the European level
588 for different parts of the pesticide regulatory framework to improve efficiency. For example,
589 there is a difference between pesticide residue definitions for enforcement (usually those
590 present in concentration databases), residue definitions for risk assessment, and the substances
591 in the CAG list, which are usually parent compounds. For example, dithiocarbamates comprise
592 all substances measured as carbon disulfide, including maneb, mancozeb, metiram, propineb,
593 thiram and ziram, whereas ziram is the only substance in the CAG. To combine both databases,
594 conversion factors should be applied to obtain the concentration of the residue definition for
595 risk assessment of the parent compound. Such conversion factors are described for example in
596 EFSA and Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues (JMPR) opinions, but no
597 harmonized database is available. Moreover, as different conversion factors may occur for
598 product-pesticide combinations, this would result in many concentration conversions to be
599 manually performed, which requires significant resources. As a pragmatic approach, the
600 conversion factors were set to 1, but may have led to an underestimation or overestimation of
601 exposure. A harmonized database with conversion factors or concentration data with a focus on
602 individual compounds would be helpful for future calculations. Another point that impacts
603 exposure is the time lag of concentration data upon regulatory changes such as new
604 authorizations and bans. Thus, concentration data are missing for new pesticides, whereas
605 exposures could be overestimated for banned pesticides. Moreover, currently, processing
606 factors are not available for all pesticide/food/process combinations. In addition, extrapolation
607 of processing factors (e.g. a processing factor available for peeling of mandarins used for
608 peeling of lemons) is not common practice. This may lead to an overestimation in cases where
609 processing lowers the pesticide concentration, e.g. peeling and juicing, or an underestimation
610 in cases where processing increases the concentration (drying of fruit, making tomato paste).
611 This is for example the case of imazalil which was mainly found in oranges, grapefruits,
612 mandarins for which no processing factor for peeling was available. It was also found in lemons
613 for which processing factors of juicing, washing and oiling were applied. More research is
614 needed to either develop new processing factors or to extrapolate processing factors between
615 food items. Matching processing factors as provided in the BfR database to the foods measured
616 in the concentration database and to foods in the food conversion table was a laborious process.
617 A harmonised table with processing factors linked to harmonise coding of SSD1 would
618 facilitate mixture selection. Another solution, which reduces uncertainty, is to measure
619 concentrations directly in food as consumed, as is the case in total diet studies (Sirot et al.,
620 2009). Running chronic exposure scenarios for adults for France and Netherlands did not affect
621 the main composition of the mixtures. There is also a need to collect information on substances

622 other than pesticides. We decided to focus on pesticides in this study because these are the
623 substances for which there are the most data regarding concentration values and CAG
624 information. However, other substances present in food such as dioxins, polychlorinated
625 biphenyls, bromated compounds, etc. could have a steatosis effect. This could lead to an
626 underestimation of the total risk related to this CAG. The originality of the proposed approach
627 is to combine information for hazard for a CAG with that on combined exposure to define
628 mixture. Under the assumption of dose-addition, the RPFs make it possible to convert the
629 exposure of all substances into the “unit toxicity” of the index compound. Although there is a
630 consensus that in most cases, dose addition is the best conservative effect estimation for
631 chemicals with exposure at low doses (Backhaus and Faust, 2012; EFSA, 2013a; Kamo and
632 Yokomizo, 2015; Kortenkamp et al., 2009). In some cases, for examples for chemicals with
633 dissimilar modes of action, this hypothesis could lead to underestimate mixture effect
634 (Altenburger et al., 2013; Borgert et al., 2012; Gregorio et al., 2013). In the absence of detailed
635 information, EFSA CAGs are currently defined on the basis of specific effects and not on their
636 mechanism or mode of action. Thus, there is uncertainty on the membership of a pesticide in a
637 CAG and on the validity of applying dose addition. Specific work related to hazard uncertainty
638 is in progress in the Euromix project to analyse the impact of CAG membership on cumulative
639 risk assessment. A probability is attributed to each substance in the CAG, and integrated in
640 calculations. Moreover, RPF values are estimated from NOAELs or LOAELs sourced from
641 bibliographic data. The BMD approach was not applied because several details on quantitative
642 data were not or only partially available from the databases (e.g.: end-points incidences in each
643 dose-groups, number of animals in each dose groups, etc.). There is a high level of uncertainty
644 around the NOAEL and LOAEL values due to the diversity of the surveys from which they
645 were collected. Thus, survey design, species, and duration of treatment could be different, and
646 lead to different level of uncertainty and to results that are difficult to compare. For liver effects,
647 100% were repeated dose studies, more than 80% were from long-term studies, and 100% were
648 from *in vivo* studies. Therefore, the liver data package can be considered homogeneous. The
649 extrapolation of NOAELs from LOAEL values for 9% of the substances can also be a source
650 of uncertainty. A ratio of three was used as it is generally used in toxicology studies dose
651 spacing regime as it was recommended in the first version of the WHO Guidance Uncertainty
652 in Hazard Assessment, the available version at the time we made the calculations. In the second
653 version (WHO, 2018) it is also proposed a ratio of 10 which can be used for future work. There
654 is also a need to define a reference compound to convert toxicity, as none of the CAG lists of
655 the DTU and EFSA indicate such index compounds. The choice of pesticide to serve as a
656 reference compound has mathematically no impact on final results. This could lead to bias if
657 there were high uncertainty on the NOAEL of the reference compound. In the present study, to
658 minimize errors, it was decided to use a well-known compound with high quality criteria as
659 listed under section 2.2.1. Modelling of uncertainty for RPFs remains research to be done in the
660 future. The EuroMix project by developing *in vitro* and *in vivo* strategies for testing mixtures
661 will contribute to greater knowledge on the toxicity of the CAG steatosis compounds. Some of
662 the pesticides prioritized in this work are now being studied for their potency separately and in
663 mixtures to test the dose-addition assumption. The EuroMix project is also studying two other
664 CAGs on developmental toxicity and endocrine disruptor.

665 During the last years, statistical developments have been proposed to identify combined
666 exposures of concern through the diet. Crépet and Tressou (2011) used a Bayesian non-
667 parametric model to determine the major mixtures classifying the population regarding their
668 exposure profiles, and then studied correlations between pesticides. More recently, Béchaux et
669 al. (2013) and Traoré et al. (2016) demonstrated the ability of the combination of non-negative
670 matrix factorisation (NMF) (Lee and Seung, 2001) with a hierarchical clustering to identify
671 principal mixtures connected with specific diets. This approach gave close results to the ones
672 obtained with the Bayesian non-parametric model (Béchaux et al., 2013), but was found to
673 produce more interpretable results in terms of mixtures and exposure systems combination
674 using the two matrices U and V. The NMF and clustering methods have also been used to define
675 dietary patterns and clusters of individual diets by Zetlaoui et al. (2011), Sy et al. (2013) and
676 Gazan et al. (2016). In this study, a modified version of the NMF method, called sparse non-
677 negative matrix under-approximation (SNMU) (Gillis and Plemmons, 2013), was used to
678 determine the main mixtures from European exposure data. It was already applied with success
679 in Traoré et al. (2018). This method is also based on the decomposition of the exposure matrix
680 into two submatrices, but used a recursive algorithm which allows us to extract exposure
681 systems one by one. From the original exposure matrix, the first rank one is extracted and
682 therefore subtracted from this matrix. The same procedure is thus applied to the new obtained
683 matrix. Thus, another rank one is extracted corresponding to the first rank for this matrix and
684 to the second rank one for the original exposure matrix. At each step, a rank one is extracted
685 from a new matrix and is identical, regardless of the number of exposure systems. Hence, this
686 algorithm has the advantage that it produces stable mixtures for a selected number of mixtures.
687 Moreover, the NMF and the SNMU are dedicated to positive and null values like exposures
688 comparing to the principal component analyses which could also be used to reduce data
689 dimension and to define mixtures.

690 As the goal of the approach is to prioritise mixtures to be assessed, the optimistic scenario
691 proposed by EFSA was chosen (EFSA, 2012). This scenario, by considering a zero value for
692 censored concentration data, makes it possible to focus on substances with quantified
693 measurements. This is a way of selecting substances with observed values, and of removing the
694 other substances, before applying the statistical method to extract mixtures. The fact that it is
695 preferable to use a more realistic optimistic scenario to define mixtures was reinforced by the
696 results obtained when using the EFSA pessimistic scenario for France as an example. New
697 substances appeared in the mixture: dazomet, endrin, friponil, ethroprophos. The imazalil
698 disappeared and the dithiocarbamates decreased. However, for dazomet for example no
699 concentration data was available thus the MRL was used. Thus, the variability in the mixture is
700 guided by the LOD and LOQ substitution and/or imputation of maximum residue limits and it
701 is attributed to uncertainty on concentration data. Boon et al. (2015) also found that the
702 pessimistic approach could lead to results far from reality, being dominated by LOD and LOQ
703 substitution and imputation of missing data by MRLs.

704 As the steatosis effect appears with long-term exposure, it was decided to study chronic
705 exposures. Acute exposure was also considered because repeated acute exposures could lead to
706 chronic effects with time.

707 The purpose of this study was to identify mixtures that are relevant to study for their
708 combined toxicological effects rather than identifying the main risk drivers. Thus, in the case
709 of a single substance composing a mixture, it was decided to restrict the exposure matrix to the
710 exposure profiles which contain mixtures in using the MCR cut-off. This was the case for all
711 countries for the acute exposure scenario. Focusing on 5% of the population with high

712 combined exposure made it possible to extract mixtures containing several compounds. A test
713 was also done to focus on 30% of the population with high combined exposure, but it produced
714 similar results of a unique substance as for the whole population. It is important to note that
715 acute exposure values are lower than chronic exposure due to the fact that only highly co-
716 exposed individuals were considered. As a result, these individuals are highly co-exposed but
717 with lower doses than other people.
718

719 **5. Conclusions**

720
721 To conclude, the proposed approach makes it possible to prioritise compounds in a given
722 CAG that need to be further studied. This may include performing further toxicological tests to
723 study modes and mechanisms of action, generating better relative potency factors and,
724 eventually, planning epidemiological surveys. As this approach is sensitive to the input data
725 and demands significant resources, it is important to continue efforts on data collection and
726 harmonisation among the different aspects within the pesticides regulatory framework, and to
727 develop methods to group substances in mixtures and to characterise the risk.

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